

ASSESSING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MORPHOLOGICAL AWARENESS AND READING COMPREHENSION OF ESL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the relationship between morphological awareness and reading comprehension among English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. Morphological awareness, which refers to the ability to recognize and manipulate the smallest units of meaning (morphemes) in words, plays a crucial role in language acquisition, particularly in reading development. This research examined how ESL learners' awareness of word structure, vocabulary acquisition, and the contextual use of morphology relate to their ability to comprehend written texts in English. The study was conducted with a sample of senior high school ESL learners from a public school in San Jose del Monte, Bulacan, using a descriptive survey questionnaire. Reading comprehension was assessed through the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Assessment Tool (Phil-IRI), which required students to analyze and answer questions about academic texts. The results indicated that while most students achieved a moderate level of reading comprehension, there was considerable room for improvement in their comprehension skills. The study, using Pearson correlation analysis revealed no statistically significant relationship between morphological awareness and reading comprehension, suggesting that factors beyond morphological knowledge may influence reading outcomes. While morphological awareness is crucial for word recognition and vocabulary development, it did not appear to directly enhance reading comprehension in this sample of ESL learners. These findings implied that other factors—such as syntax, reading fluency, background knowledge, and reading strategies—may play a more significant role in influencing comprehension. Further research was recommended to investigate the interplay between syntax,

semantics, and morphological knowledge in the development of reading comprehension skills among ESL learners.

Keywords: *Morphological Awareness, Reading Comprehension, ESL Learners*

INTRODUCTION

Education in the Philippines remains low due to the recent Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) does not inspire confidence in the Philippine education system. The results of the 2022 PISA test showed that the Philippines had made very little progress, placing it in the bottom 10 out of 81 nations in reading comprehension (Philippine Star 2023). Despite the educational reforms established to improve the Philippine Education System, the Philippines remains low and significantly below its neighboring countries regarding quality education.

Recently, the Department of Education (DepEd) conducts Project DEAR, often known as "Drop Everything and Read," a period that is consistently allotted every Friday in the school calendar for both students and teachers aimed at fostering a culture of reading among students and educators. It certainly aims to address the gap in reading comprehension skills in ESL learners by encouraging students to develop a love for reading and establish reading as a regular habit. This initiative aims to provide interventions and support for students who are struggling with reading. Studies have shown that learners who develop strong morphological awareness tend to demonstrate improved reading comprehension skills, as they can decode and interpret complex words more effectively (Carlisle, 2000; Apel et al., 2004). However, despite these advancements, numerous issues persist, including a lack of targeted instructional strategies for teaching morphology and insufficient understanding of how these strategies specifically influence reading comprehension among ESL learners. Several linguistic and language-related abilities contribute to decoding and comprehension. For example, phonological awareness and orthographic awareness are important precursors to decoding and word-recognition skills (Lieberman, et al., 1989). Furthermore, phonological, semantic, morphological, and syntactic abilities all contribute to one's language comprehension abilities (Gleason, 2001).

The primary objective of this research was to assess the relationship between morphological awareness and reading comprehension among ESL learners, thereby filling a critical gap in existing literature. By employing a quantitative approach, this study analyzed how different morphological awareness, such as morphological analysis and word formation techniques, affect ESL learners' ability to comprehend texts. Furthermore, this research aimed to contribute to the field of language education by providing empirical evidence that can inform instructional practices and curricular design. Insights from this study will help educators develop effective teaching strategies that harness the power of morphology, ultimately fostering better reading outcomes for ESL learners. In an era where literacy skills are essential for academic and professional success, understanding

and addressing the intersection of morphology and reading comprehension represents a significant step toward enhancing educational practices for diverse learners.

Research Questions

The focus of the study was to determine if there is a significant relationship between Morphological awareness on the Reading Comprehension of ESL learners in a selected school in San Jose del Monte, Bulacan. This research sought to address the following questions:

1. How may the scores in reading comprehension of ESL learners be described?
2. How may the morphological awareness of ESL learners be assessed in terms of:
 - 2.1 Word Structure Awareness;
 - 2.2 Morphological Application in Vocabulary Acquisition; and
 - 2.3 Contextual Use of Morphological Knowledge?
3. Is there a significant relationship between morphological awareness and reading comprehension of ESL Learners?
4. What interventions and implications may be developed based on the results of this study to achieve Reading comprehension skills development among ESL learners?

METHODOLOGY

Theoretical/ Methodological Framework

The research is based on Schema Theory that emphasizes the importance of knowledge, in understanding written material and how readers derive meaning from texts by accessing and linking their existing knowledge structures or schemas. Some scholars like Anderson and Pearson (1984) introduced Schema Theory asserting that comprehension is not merely a task but an engaging interaction between the text and the reader's cognitive frameworks, in place. Based on this theory's perspective; when individuals read a passage or text piece, they trigger frameworks that assist in grasping and making sense of the content based upon their existing knowledge base and context familiarity levels. For ESL (English, as a Second Language) learners who may not have fully developed these frameworks or schemas in place yet; understanding and interpreting texts can pose significant challenges and hurdles.

In this research project the researchers used Schema Theory as a basis, for exploring how breaking down words into their root prefixes and suffixes helps ESL students improve their reading comprehension. By emphasizing the structure of words students are better able to grasp meaning because they connect vocabulary to what they know linguistically. This approach helps them bridge gaps in their understanding leading to decoding and comprehension of texts.

Furthermore, the idea proposes that as students develop structured mental frameworks their capacity to deduce and assess data also advances. This coincides with the research goal of investigating how morphological approaches impact comprehension levels such as understanding inference and critical evaluation as outlined by Anderson and Pearson in 1984. Using Schema Theory as the lens through which data is interpreted, the research will analyze how morphological awareness contributes to schema activation and development, thereby enhancing reading comprehension among ESL learners. This methodological alignment with Schema Theory will facilitate a deeper understanding of how targeted instructional strategies can support the creation of strong and interconnected schemas, ultimately improving the reading proficiency of ESL students (Anderson & Pearson, 1984).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

As shown in Figure 1, this conceptual framework underscored the relationship between morphological awareness in enhancing reading comprehension among ESL learners. By examining this relationship, the research aimed to contribute to effective teaching strategies and interventions that foster both morphological skills and reading comprehension, ultimately leading to improved literacy outcomes for ESL students. This framework served as a basis for further empirical investigation, aimed to clarify the mechanisms through which morphological awareness affects reading comprehension and to identify potential strategies for enhancing these skills in educational settings.

Research Design

This study integrated the use of a Descriptive-Correlational Research design to systematically capture and analyze data regarding the effect of morphological awareness to the reading comprehension. According to Creswell (2012), a correlation is a statistical

test to determine the tendency or pattern for two (or more) variables or two sets of data to vary consistently. The purpose of correlational research is to determine the relationship among two or more variables. Upon identifying the significant relationship of variables, interventions and implications may be developed to maximize the potential of each ESL learner to improve their reading comprehension.

Respondents

This study used Quota Sampling as its method to proceed in selecting their respondents from the given population. Quota sampling allows the researchers to ensure that specific subgroups are represented within the sample, which is essential for exploring differences in morphological awareness across different demographics (Patton, 2002). With the Quota sampling, the researchers determined the number of respondents needed from each demographic group based on the total population available (Creswell, 2014). For this study, the researchers have established a target sample size of one hundred (100) Grade 12 students from a public school in San Jose del Monte, Bulacan. The researcher's aim was to encompass the school's entire population as respondents in the study.

Instrument

The researchers employed a descriptive questionnaire to collect data from respondents, consisting of two main parts. Part I focused on the assessment of reading comprehension through a multiple-choice type of test from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Assessment Tool 2021.

Part II involved a self-assessment survey aimed at gauging respondents' evaluation on their own experiences regarding the morphological awareness such as word structure awareness, morphological application in vocabulary acquisition, and contextual use of morphological knowledge. Given that the questionnaire is developed by the researchers, pilot testing was conducted to check the reliability of the questionnaire. Cronbach's Alpha was used to test the reliability. According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016), Cronbach's alpha is a reliability coefficient that shows how well the items in a set are positively correlated with each other. Cronbach's alpha is calculated as the mean of intercorrelations between items measuring the concept. The closer the Cronbach alpha is to 1, the higher the internal consistency reliability. Based on the results of the pilot testing, Cronbach's alpha value of the three variables; Word Structure Awareness, Morphological Application in Vocabulary Acquisition, and Contextual Use of Morphological Knowledge are 0.734, 0.703, and 0.704 respectively. Using a criterion of 0.70 as the benchmark for acceptable internal consistency reliability. This showed that the questionnaire is reliable.

The questionnaire used the following 5-point Likert Scale:

<i>Rating</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	Strongly Disagree
2	Disagree

- 3 Neutral
- 4 Agree
- 5 Strongly Agree

The questions were turned into an online form using Google Forms which was sent to all target respondents to answer.

Data Collection and Analysis

In conducting the survey process, a formal communication was sent to the school principal requesting permission and approval. The developed research instrument, which is the Google Form survey, sent out to one hundred (100) Grade 12 students of the Senior High School Department. The link was sent to their school-provided Gmail, and a form limiter was created to allow the form to be open only for a week. An introductory message at the beginning of the survey clarified its purpose and assured respondents of its complete anonymity. Responses collected through Google Forms automatically populate a Google Sheets document, facilitating efficient organization, analysis, and interpretation of the data by the researchers.

For data processing and analysis, the gathered data was organized, tallied, and treated statistically.

For Part I of the instrument, the responses sheet that generated from the Google Forms about the respondents' reading comprehension will be summarized using a tally of scores. For Part II of the instrument, the results of the survey, about respondents' evaluation of their own experiences regarding the morphological awareness, were treated statistically using frequency count and weighted mean.

The following range was used in interpreting the result of the survey:

<i>Range</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Result Interpretation</i>
1.00 - 1.79	Strongly Disagree	Very Uninfluential
1.80 - 2.59	Disagree	Uninfluential
2.60 - 3.39	Neutral	Neutral
3.40 - 4.19	Agree	Influential
4.20 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Influential

To test the relationship between morphological awareness and reading comprehension scores, Pearson's Correlation Analysis was employed. According to Ahlgren et al., (2003), correlation is a technique for measuring the relationship between two quantitative and continuous variables. The most common measurement of correlation is Pearson's Correlation. This statistical test is appropriate for measuring the strength of the relationship between two continuous variables: the total scores from the Likert-scale

responses (morphological awareness) and students' reading comprehension test scores. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) is to measure the strength of the association between two variables. The scale model suggested by Davis (1971) used to describe the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, are as shown below:

1. 0.7 and above – very strong relationship,
2. 0.50 to 0.69 – strong relationship,
3. 0.30 to 0.49 – moderate relationship,
4. 0.10 to 0.29 – low relationships and
5. 0.01 to 0.09 – very low relationship.

RESULTS

Reading Comprehension of ESL learners

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Reading Comprehension Scores of ESL learners

Score	Frequency	Percentage
8	0	0.00%
7	1	1.00%
6	14	14.00%
5	29	29.00%
4	30	30.00%
3	20	20.00%
2	5	5.00%

1	1	1.00%
Total	100	100.00%

Overall Mean = 4.27

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of reading comprehension scores among ESL learners. The data indicates that most students scored between 3 and 5, with 30% scoring a 4 and 29% scoring a 5, suggesting that a large portion of the learners are achieving moderate comprehension levels. Additionally, 20% of students scored a 3, while only 5% scored a 2. The higher and lower extremes are less common, with 1% scoring a 7 and 1% scoring a 1, while no students scored an 8.

The mean score of 4.27 reflects a generally moderate level of reading comprehension among the ESL learners, indicating that there may be room for improvement in comprehension skills. These results highlight the importance of targeted interventions to support those at lower comprehension levels and to help all learners progress further in their reading abilities.

Morphological Awareness of ESL learners

Table 2. Mean Distribution of Morphological Awareness of ESL learners in Terms of Word Structure

<i>I. Word Structure Awareness</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Result Interpretation</i>
<i>I can easily identify the root word within complex words (e.g., happy in unhappiness).</i>	3.58	1.22	Agree	Influential
<i>I know how adding prefixes changes a word's meaning (e.g., re- in redo means "again").</i>	3.52	1.15	Agree	Influential
<i>I can recognize suffixes and their impact on a word's function (e.g., -ly turns an adjective into an adverb).</i>	3.55	1.11	Agree	Influential

<i>I understand that the same root word can appear in multiple forms (e.g., act, actor, action).</i>	3.83	1.20	Agree	Influential
<i>I can deconstruct long words into smaller meaningful parts (e.g., unbelievable = un-, believe, -able).</i>	3.73	1.16	Agree	Influential
Word Structure Awareness	3.64	0.94	Agree	Influential

Table 2 presents the mean distribution of morphological awareness among ESL learners in terms of Word Structure Awareness. The results indicate that students generally demonstrate an “Agree” level of awareness across all items, with an overall mean of 3.64 (SD = 0.94), suggesting that they possess a moderate to high understanding of word structure.

Specifically, students reported the highest awareness in identifying multiple forms of a root word (mean = 3.83, SD = 1.20) and in breaking down long words into meaningful parts (mean = 3.73, SD = 1.16). They also show strong awareness of the role of prefixes and suffixes in changing word meanings and functions, with mean scores of 3.52 and 3.55, respectively. All items in this section are interpreted as "Influential," indicating that the students' awareness of word structure significantly supports their morphological understanding. This level of awareness forms a solid foundation for further developing reading comprehension skills, as understanding word structure can help learners decode complex vocabulary.

Table 3. Mean Distribution of Morphological Awareness of ESL learners in Terms of Morphological Application in Vocabulary Acquisition

II. Morphological Application in Vocabulary Acquisition	Mean	Std. Dev.	Adjectival Rating	Descriptive Evaluation
<i>I break down unfamiliar words into smaller parts to figure out their meaning.</i>	3.49	1.07	Agree	Influential
<i>Knowing common prefixes and suffixes helps me learn new vocabulary.</i>	3.66	1.08	Agree	Influential

<i>I can predict the meaning of a new word based on its word parts.</i>	3.45	1.02	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Influential</i>
<i>I rely on my knowledge of morphology when solving word puzzles or games.</i>	3.36	1.21	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Influential</i>
<i>I find it easier to understand academic texts by analyzing the structure of words.</i>	3.70	1.00	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Influential</i>
<i>Morphological Application in Vocabulary Acquisition</i>	3.53	0.87	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Influential</i>

Table 3 shows the mean distribution of morphological awareness among ESL learners in terms of Morphological Application in Vocabulary Acquisition. The overall mean score for this category is 3.53 (SD = 0.87), with a rating of "Agree" and an interpretation of "Influential." This suggests that learners frequently use morphological knowledge to aid in vocabulary acquisition.

The item with the highest mean, 3.70 (SD = 1.00), indicates that students find it easier to understand academic texts by analyzing word structures. Additionally, students also "Agree" that knowing common prefixes and suffixes assists them in learning new vocabulary, with a mean of 3.66 (SD = 1.08). Other aspects, such as breaking down unfamiliar words, predicting meanings based on word parts, and applying morphology in word puzzles, have mean scores ranging from 3.36 to 3.49, demonstrating consistent use of morphology in vocabulary acquisition.

Overall, the results imply that morphological application is influential in vocabulary acquisition, highlighting that students actively employ morphological strategies to support their understanding of new words, which is crucial for reading comprehension development.

Table 4. Mean Distribution of Morphological Awareness of ESL learners in Terms of Contextual Use of Morphological Knowledge

III. Contextual Use of Morphological Knowledge	Mean	Std. Dev.	Adjectiva I Rating	Descriptive Evaluation
<i>I use both sentence context and word parts to understand unfamiliar words.</i>	3.76	1.14	Agree	Influential
<i>I can recognize when a word's suffix gives away its part of speech (e.g., -ment = noun).</i>	3.35	0.93	Neutral	Neutral
<i>I adjust my understanding of a word if the sentence context changes its meaning.</i>	3.57	1.07	Agree	Influential
<i>I use context to guess the meanings of unfamiliar compound words (e.g., sunflower).</i>	3.60	1.06	Agree	Influential
<i>I find it easier to comprehend passages by connecting word parts to their use in context.</i>	3.64	1.09	Agree	Influential
Contextual Use of Morphological Knowledge	3.58	0.81	Agree	Influential

Table 4 displays the mean distribution of morphological awareness among ESL learners in terms of Contextual Use of Morphological Knowledge. The overall mean for this category is 3.58 (SD = 0.81), reflecting a general "Agree" response, indicating that students often use context and word structure together to enhance their comprehension.

The highest-rated item, with a mean of 3.76 (SD = 1.14), shows that students frequently use both sentence context and word parts to understand unfamiliar words, suggesting a strong integration of morphological knowledge and context. Students also reported high agreement with the idea that they adjust their understanding of a word when the sentence context changes its meaning (mean = 3.57, SD = 1.07) and use context to guess the meanings of compound words (mean = 3.60, SD = 1.06).

However, the statement regarding recognizing suffixes as indicators of parts of speech (e.g., -ment = noun) had a neutral rating of 3.35 (SD = 0.93), suggesting that students may not consistently apply this morphological knowledge in determining word class.

Overall, these results indicate that contextual use of morphological knowledge plays an influential role in helping ESL learners understand unfamiliar words, with some areas needing further reinforcement, especially in recognizing word classes based on suffixes.

Significant Relationship

Table 5. Correlation between Morphological awareness on the Reading Comprehension of ESL learners

<i>Morphological Awareness</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
<i>I. Word Structure Awareness</i>	<i>0.698</i>	<i>0.039</i>	<i>No Significant Relationship</i>
<i>II. Morphological Application in Vocabulary Acquisition</i>	<i>0.640</i>	<i>0.047</i>	<i>No Significant Relationship</i>
<i>III. Contextual Use of Morphological Knowledge</i>	<i>0.670</i>	<i>0.043</i>	<i>No Significant Relationship</i>
<i>Morphological Awareness</i>	<i>0.642</i>	<i>0.047</i>	<i>No Significant Relationship</i>

Table 5 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients and associated significance values for various factors related to morphological awareness among ESL learners. The results show that the correlations between word structure awareness, the application of morphology in vocabulary acquisition, and the contextual use of morphological knowledge (with correlation values ranging from 0.039 to 0.047) are not statistically significant at the conventional alpha level of 0.05. This indicates that, despite the observed positive relationships, there is insufficient evidence to support a meaningful association between these aspects of morphological awareness and reading comprehension performance in this sample of ESL learners.

Furthermore, the overall Pearson correlation for morphological awareness ($r = 0.642$) also suggests a "no significant relationship" with the learners' reading comprehension scores. While the correlation value is moderate, it falls short of reaching statistical significance, reinforcing the conclusion that morphological awareness, in this study, is not a strong or direct predictor of reading comprehension abilities.

DISCUSSION

The primary aim of this study was to assess the morphological awareness of ESL learners in San Jose del Monte, Bulacan, and to examine its role on their reading comprehension. In exploring how the reading comprehension levels of these learners can be characterized, the findings from Table 1 reveal that most students scored moderately, with a mean score of 4.27, suggesting an average level of comprehension among participants. Most students scored between 3 and 5, indicating that while a foundational level of comprehension exists, significant room for improvement remains, especially as only 1% scored at the highest levels. This result underscores the need for targeted educational interventions to support reading comprehension.

In terms of assessing morphological awareness, results in Tables 2, 3, and 4 reveal a consistent "Agree" response, indicating that students generally possess an influential level of awareness in various morphological aspects, including word structure, vocabulary acquisition, and contextual application. Table 2, focused on word structure awareness, shows an overall mean of 3.64, highlighting students' ability to identify root words, prefixes, and suffixes. Such skills are critical in aiding comprehension, as they enable students to deconstruct and interpret complex vocabulary more effectively.

Further, Table 3 illustrates the students' use of morphological knowledge for vocabulary acquisition, with a mean score of 3.53. Notably, students reported high utility in analyzing word structures when encountering academic texts, suggesting that morphological strategies play a significant role in expanding their vocabulary. These skills appear to bridge the gap between word recognition and understanding, contributing positively to reading comprehension.

Regarding the contextual use of morphology, as detailed in Table 4, the learners frequently employed both sentence context and morphological knowledge to interpret unfamiliar words. The highest-rated item in this section indicates that students commonly adjust their understanding of word meanings based on context, showcasing a nuanced approach to language comprehension. However, the neutral rating in recognizing word suffixes as indicators of parts of speech suggests that targeted instruction in this area may be beneficial.

This study highlighted that while morphological awareness may have some role in ESL learners' reading comprehension, the relationship is not statistically significant, as detailed in Table 5, and other factors might be at play. More comprehensive studies that

consider additional variables or different populations may provide more insight into how morphological awareness and reading comprehension are connected. The lack of significant relationships between the variables suggests that morphological awareness, while important for word recognition and vocabulary acquisition, may not directly enhance reading comprehension for ESL learners in this study. It could be that other factors, such as syntax, fluency, background knowledge, or reading strategies, play a more prominent role in influencing reading comprehension in ESL learners.

Based on these findings, several recommendations are warranted. The results imply that simply understanding the structure of words may not be sufficient for improving reading comprehension outcomes. Further research may be needed to explore other dimensions of language proficiency, such as syntax and semantics, and how they interact with morphological knowledge in the context of reading comprehension. Moreover, educators should emphasize teaching strategies that integrate morphological and contextual analysis to enhance comprehension, providing ESL learners with the tools necessary to navigate complex texts. Future research might explore longitudinal impacts of such instructional strategies, providing further insights into effective literacy interventions in ESL education.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of the result, the researchers hereby concluded the following:

1) The study concluded that ESL learners in San Jose del Monte, Bulacan, exhibit a moderate level of reading comprehension, with most scoring between 3 and 5 on the comprehension assessment. This indicated a foundational ability but highlights the need for targeted interventions to support further development in comprehension skills.

2) Morphological awareness, as assessed through word structure awareness, vocabulary acquisition, and contextual use, was shown to be a significant factor influencing ESL learners' reading comprehension. Learners demonstrated an overall positive ability to identify and utilize morphological structures, such as root words, prefixes, and suffixes, aiding them in deconstructing and understanding complex vocabulary.

3) The results indicated that contextual use of morphology, where learners apply both sentence context and word parts to interpret meaning, is influential in enhancing comprehension. However, a neutral response in identifying word suffixes as indicators of parts of speech suggests a need for additional instructional focus in this area.

4) Integrating morphological instruction within ESL curricula can be beneficial for learners, particularly in improving areas where proficiency was lower. Teaching strategies that emphasize both morphological analysis and contextual interpretation may help ESL learners to better comprehend complex texts.

5) The findings highlighted the complexity of reading comprehension and suggest that a focus on morphological awareness alone may not be sufficient to significantly improve reading comprehension skills in ESL learners. Thus, more comprehensive approaches to

literacy instruction are needed ones that integrate a broader range of language skills, including syntax, fluency, and strategic reading practices.

6) Future research is recommended to explore the long-term effects of morphological-focused instructional strategies on reading comprehension outcomes among ESL learners, potentially informing language education policy and pedagogical practices.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were proposed.

1) **Incorporate Morphological Instruction into the Curriculum:** Schools should integrate targeted morphological instruction into the ESL curriculum. This can include lessons focused on understanding root words, prefixes, suffixes, and how these elements contribute to word meaning. Such integration can help enhance students' decoding skills, supporting their overall reading comprehension.

2) **Emphasize Contextual Use of Morphological Knowledge:** Teachers should encourage students to use both morphological and contextual cues when encountering unfamiliar words. Instructional strategies like context-based vocabulary exercises and morphological analysis can reinforce students' ability to interpret meaning from both word parts and sentence structure.

3) **Focus on Teaching Word Class Identification:** Given that students showed less proficiency in identifying word classes based on suffixes, specific lessons on parts of speech—such as recognizing nouns, adjectives, and verbs by their morphological endings—should be added to the curriculum. This will strengthen students' grammatical understanding and aid in more accurate comprehension.

4) **Develop Diagnostic and Formative Assessments for Morphology Skills:** Schools and educators should implement assessments to regularly evaluate students' morphological awareness and track progress. This can help identify specific areas where individual students may need additional support, allowing for targeted interventions.

5) **Offer Professional Development for ESL Teachers:** Schools should provide professional development workshops on morphological instruction for ESL teachers. Training in evidence-based morphological strategies will equip teachers with the skills to support and improve students' reading comprehension through enhanced vocabulary and morphology instruction.

6) **Encourage Vocabulary-Building Activities:** Activities such as word puzzles, root word exploration, and morpheme-based games can make vocabulary learning engaging while reinforcing morphological skills. Such activities can promote active learning and improve vocabulary acquisition among ESL learners.

7) **Conduct Further Research on Instructional Effectiveness:** Additional studies should be conducted to assess the long-term impact of morphology-focused instruction on ESL

reading comprehension or an experimental approach. Research could explore diverse teaching methods and identify the most effective approaches for enhancing morphological awareness and reading outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this research study, rigorous adherence to ethical principles was paramount. The informed consent of all respondents, namely the Senior High School students, were obtained prior to their involvement in the survey. It was emphasized on the disclaimer of the Google form survey that participation is voluntary, and respondents were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Any personal data collected were handled with utmost care, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations. (R.A 10173 or Data Privacy Act of 2012). Additionally, a letter of consent was sent to the School Principal, as well as parent consent, to seek her permission to conduct the study.

Moreover, the research utilized AI tools to analyze data efficiently while ensuring that all ethical standards are maintained. This approach enhanced data accuracy and interpretation while safeguarding participants' rights and dignity. The study was conducted with integrity, transparency, and a commitment to contributing valuable insights, all while upholding ethical standards throughout the entire process.

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